

PMR POLYIMIDE PREPREG WITH IMPROVED TACK CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract

Current PMR Polyimide prepreg technology utilizes methanol or ethanol solvents for preparation of the PMR prepreg solutions. The volatility of these solvents limits the tack and drape retention characteristics of unprotected prepreg exposed to ambient conditions. Studies conducted to achieve PMR 15 Polyimide prepreg with improved tack and drape characteristics are described. Improved tack and drape retention were obtained by incorporation of an additional monomer. The effects of various levels of the added monomer on the thermo-oxidative stability and mechanical properties of graphite fiber reinforced PMR 15 composites exposed and tested at 316° C (600° F) are discussed.

Introduction

Ever since their introduction in the early to mid-fifties the inherent intractibility of high temperature polymers has limited their usefulness as matrix resins for fiber reinforced composites. State-of-the-art high temperature polymer matrix composites, that is, composites having void contents in the range of 5 to 10 percent, can be achieved only by employing complicated processing cycles.

In response to the need for high temperature polymers with improved processability investigators at the NASA Lewis Research Center developed the so-called PMR Polyimides (Ref. 1). In the approach used to prepare these highly processable polyimides in situ Polymerization of Monomer Reactants (PMR) occurs on the surface of the reinforcing fibers. The advantages and versatility of the PMR approach has been reviewed (Ref. 2). At the present time two general types of PMR Polyimides each differing in the stoichiometry and chemical composition have been identified. Both versions, the earlier PMR 15 (first generation) as well as the more recently developed second generation material (PMR II) (Ref. 3) employ low boiling point alcoholic solvents. The volatility of these solvents, which is highly desirable for obtaining void-free composites, limits the tack and drape retention characteristics of unprotected prepreg exposed to the ambient.

The purpose of this investigation was to identify PMR Polyimide compositions which provide prepreg materials with improved tack and drape retention characteristics. This report describes studies in which various amounts of reactive diluents containing an olefinic double bond were added to the PMR monomer reactant solutions. The tack and drape retention characteristics of graphite fiber prepreg exposed at ambient conditions were qualitatively measured. Composites were fabricated and their mechanical properties were determined at room temperature and 316° C (600° F). Composites weight loss and mechanical properties retention characteristics as a function of exposure time in air at 316° C (600° F) were also determined.

Experimental Procedures

Monomers

The monomers used in this study are shown in Table I. The monomethyl ester of 5-norbornene-2,3-dicarboxylic acid (NE) and 4,4'-methylenedianiline

TABLE I. - MONOMERS USED FOR POLYIMIDE SYNTHESIS

Structure	Name	Abbreviation
	Monomethyl ester of 5-norbornene-2,3-dicarboxylic acid	NE
	Dimethyl ester of 3,3',4,4'-benzophenone-tetracarboxylic acid	BTDE
	Diethyl ester of 3,3',4,4'-benzophenone-tetracarboxylic acid	BTDET
	4,4'-Methylenedianiline	MDA

(MDA) were purchased from commercial sources. The dimethyl and diethyl esters of 3,3',4,4'-benzophenonetetracarboxylic acid (BTDE and BTDET) were synthesized by refluxing a suspension of the calculated amount of 3,3',4,4'-benzophenonetetracarboxylic dianhydride in the calculated amount of either methanol or ethanol until the solid had dissolved and then for an additional 2 hours to give a 50 weight percent solution of BTDE or BTDET.

The reactive diluents used in this study are shown in Table II. These monomers were purchased from commercial sources.

Preparation of PMR Solutions

PMR reactant solutions were prepared at room temperature by dissolving the monomers and calculated amounts of the reactive diluent in either anhy-

TABLE II. - REACTIVE DILUENTS

Structure	Name	Boiling point		Abbreviation
		°C	°F	
	Styrene	145	293	STY
	Bicyclo[2.2.1]hepta-2,5-diene	89	192	BHD
	1-Vinyl-2-pyrrolidinone	a		NVP

^a Polymerizes above 135° C (275° F)

drous methanol or ethanol to form 50 weight percent solutions. The monomer stoichiometry for PMR 15 solutions using methanol (designated PMR 15M) was 2 NE/3.087 MDA/2.087 BTDE. The stoichiometry for PMR solutions using ethanol (designated PMR 15E) was 2 NE/3.087 MDA/2.087 BTDET. The amount of added reactive diluent is expressed as percent of total monomer weight.

Composite Fabrication

Prepreg tapes were made by drum-winding and impregnating Hercules HTS graphite fiber with the PMR monomer solutions to yield prepregs containing 45 percent monomers and 55 percent fiber by weight. The prepreg tapes were dried on the drum at about 50° C (122° F) for 1 hour. The tapes were removed from the drum, cut into 7.62 cm by 20.32 cm (3 in. by 8 in.) plies and stacked unidirectionally, 11 plies thick. The prepreg stack was placed in a preforming mold and staged at 120° C (248° F) for 3 hours under a pressure of 6.9×10^2 N/m² (0.1 psi). Composites were molded by placing the staged prepreg into a matched metal die preheated to 232° C (450° F). Following a dwell time of 10 minutes, a pressure of 3.45×10^6 N/m² (500 psi) was applied, and the temperature was increased to 316° C (600° F) at a rate of 5.5° C (10° F) per minute. Pressure and temperature were maintained for 1 hour. After curing, all composites were postcured for 16 hours at 316° C (600° F).

Composite Testing

Prior to specimen preparation all laminates were inspected using an ultrasonic C-scan technique. Flexural strength tests were performed using a three point loading fixture with a fixed span of 5.08 cm (2 in.). The rate of center loading was 0.127 cm/min. (0.05 in./min.). The thickness of the laminates ranged from 0.1905 cm (0.075 in.) to 0.2159 cm (0.085 in.), resulting in a span/depth ratio of 24 to 27. Interlaminar shear strength tests were conducted at a constant span/depth ratio of 5. All mechanical property values are averages of 3 tests. The flexural property values were normalized to 55 volume percent fiber. The fiber content of the laminates was determined by digestion with H₂SO₄/H₂O₂. Glass transition temperatures were determined with a thermomechanical analysis (TMA) apparatus. The weight loss of the laminates was determined by isothermal exposure at 316° C (600° F) in a forced draft oven with an air change rate of 100 cm³/min.

Prepreg Tack and Drape

Qualitative tack measurement was made by pressing together two prepreg sections, then pulling the sections apart. Loss of tack was indicated by lack of adhesion.

Qualitative drape measurement was made by bending the prepreg perpendicular to the fiber direction. Loss of drape was indicated by stiffening and cracking of the prepreg.

Results and Discussion

Prepreg Tack and Drape

The handling characteristics of prepreg materials are most frequently described using the following terms: (1) tack, (2) tack retention or tack out-life, and (3) drape. Tack describes the tendency of the prepreg to adhere to itself, or stated differently, to exhibit the behavior of a pressure sensitive adhesive. Tack retention, or tack out-life, refers to the time interval during which unprotected prepreg exposed to ambient conditions retains its tack. Drape denotes the ability of the prepreg to conform to contours without exhibiting cracking.

PMR Polyimide prepreg materials prepared from methanol or ethanol solutions of the monomer reactants exhibit adequate initial tack and drape. After exposure at ambient conditions for about 24 hours the prepreg prepared from methanol PMR solutions loses its tack and becomes somewhat boardy. Under similar exposure conditions the ethanol based prepreg retains its tack and drape characteristics for about 48 hours.

The volatility (low boiling point) of the alcohols employed as solvents in state-of-the-art PMR Polyimides is responsible for the limited tack and drape retention characteristics exhibited by PMR prepreg materials. An obvious approach to obtain improved tack and drape retention characteristics would be to replace all or at least a portion of the alcohol with a higher boiling point solvent. High boiling point aprotic solvents, such as N-methylpyrrolidone or dimethylformamide, were considered to be unsuitable. Composite processing difficulties encountered when using these solvents have been discussed previously (Ref. 2).

To improve the tack and drape retention characteristics of PMR prepreg, our approach in this study was to incorporate an additional, or fourth, monomer to the standard alcohol PMR solutions. Monomers which met the following criteria were selected for study: (1) The boiling point of the monomer needed to be greater than that of either methanol or ethanol, (2) The monomer needed to be compatible with the state-of-the-art PMR formulations, and (3) The molecular structure of the monomer needed to contain an olefinic double bond.

The reasons for criteria one and two are fairly straightforward. The third criterion was established to force the selection of monomers which could possibly enter into the final addition curing reaction and thus not be released as void causing volatile materials. To distinguish the fourth monomer from the other monomers used in formulating the PMR solutions we have chosen to refer to the added monomer as a "reactive diluent" (see Table II).

Table III summarizes the qualitative observations of the tack and drape retention characteristics of prepreg from PMR 15E (ethanol) and PMR 15M

TABLE III. - SUMMARY OF QUALITATIVE OBSERVATIONS OF PREPREG TACK AND DRAPE RETENTION CHARACTERISTICS

Monomer/Reactive system/diluent	Diluent level, w/o	Time to tack loss, days	Time to drape loss, days
PMR 15E/None	--	2	3-4
PMR 15E/Styrene	1	2	3-4
PMR 15E/Styrene	2	2-3	4-5
PMR 15E/Styrene	5	4	5-6
PMR 15M/None	--	1	1
PMR 15M/Styrene	5	1	1
PMR 15M/Styrene	10	1-2	1-2
PMR 15M/Styrene	20	2	2-3
PMR 15M/BHD	5	1	1
PMR 15M/BHD	10	1	1
PMR 15M/BHD	20	1-2	1-2
PMR 15M/NVP	5	1	1
PMR 15M/NVP	10	1	1
PMR 15M/NVP	20	1-2	2

(methanol) solutions containing the various types and amounts of reactive diluents. The reactive diluent which provided the most marked improvement in prepreg tack and drape retention was styrene. The addition of 5 w/o styrene to a PMR 15E solution doubled the prepreg tack out-life. Although an improvement in drape retention was observed, the level of improvement was less than that observed for tack retention. As the solvent evaporates the prepreg surface assumes a skin-like quality. The lack of agreement between tack and drape retention may be due to the presence of the skin-like surface which restricts the flexibility of the prepreg, or more simply to inherent deficiencies in the qualitative tests used to assess tack and drape retention. Styrene additions of 1 and 2 w/o to the PMR 15E solutions resulted in only marginal improvements to the tack and drape retention.

Prepreg prepared from the more highly volatile PMR 15M solutions required an addition of 20 w/o styrene to effect a noticeable improvement in prepreg tack and drape retention. Styrene additions of 5 and 10 w/o had little or no beneficial effect on retention of tack and drape.

The addition of either BHD or NVP to PMR 15M solutions, even at levels of up to 20 w/o, provided only minimal improvements to tack and drape retention. Because of these results prepregs were not prepared from PMR 15E solutions containing BHD or NVP.

Attempts to provide a quantitative measure of tack and drape retention by monitoring the variation of prepreg volatile content with time and correlating these data with the qualitative observations proved to be unsuccessful.

TABLE IV. - PHYSICAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF PMR 15/HTS GRAPHITE FIBER COMPOSITES

Composite/Reactive diluent	Diluent level in PMR solution, w/o	Fiber v/o	Tg,		Mechanical properties at 24° C (75° F)					
					Interlaminar shear strength		Flexural strength		Flexural modulus of elasticity	
			°C	°F	N/m ²	ksi	N/m ²	ksi	N/m ²	ksi
PMR 15E/None	--	60.0	346	655	106.2×10 ⁶	15.4	144.1×10 ⁷	209	106.9×10 ⁹	15.5×10 ³
PMR 15E/Styrene	1	57.9	336	637	100.7	14.6	146.2	212	108.9	15.8
PMR 15E/Styrene	2	59.1	344	651	99.3	14.4	143.4	208	108.9	15.8
PMR 15E/Styrene	5	58.3	357	675	100.0	14.5	155.8	226	113.8	16.5
PMR 15M/None	--	56.0	336	637	97.2	14.1	160.7	233	112.4	16.3
PMR 15M/Styrene	5	59.7	337	639	105.5	15.3	153.1	222	111.0	16.1
PMR 15M/Styrene	10	59.3	331	628	112.4	16.3	152.4	221	112.4	16.3
PMR 15M/Styrene	20	59.6	348	658	103.4	15.0	147.6	214	109.6	15.9
PMR 15M/BHD	5	55.6	340	644	95.8	13.9	149.6	217	108.9	15.8
PMR 15M/BHD	10	56.3	345	653	98.6	14.3	148.9	216	105.5	15.3
PMR 15M/BHD	20	58.1	342	648	88.9	12.9	155.1	225	113.1	16.4

Composite Properties

Improvements in prepreg tack and drape retention characteristics would be of no practical value if the composite thermal and mechanical properties were adversely affected. Composite data are summarized in Table IV. Composites prepared from prepreg derived from PMR 15E and PMR 15M solutions are designated PMR 15E and PMR 15M, respectively. Data are not presented in Table IV for the PMR 15M/NVP because the composites had a relatively high void content. The data given in Table IV show that the use of styrene and BHD as reactive diluents did not have an adverse effect on room temperature composite properties. These results indicate that the reactive diluent had either volatilized prior to final curing of the composites or had entered into the addition reaction which occurs during final curing. Studies to establish the exact nature of the interactions, if any, between the reactive diluents and the PMR Polyimides are in progress.

Figures 1 to 8 show the effects of isothermal exposure in air at 316° C (600° F) on the properties of PMR 15E/styrene and PMR 15M/styrene composites. Isothermal exposure data for PMR 15M/BHD composites are not shown. To aid the interpretation of data and because most of the data points are fairly well clustered together, curves have only been drawn through the data points for the control samples (composites prepared from prepreg without added styrene).

Weight loss data for PMR 15E composites exposed in air at 316° C (600° F) are presented in Figure 1. The figure shows that additions of styrene to the PMR solutions in the range of 1 to 5 w/o had no appreciable deleterious effect on the thermooxidative stability of the composites. The weight loss differences between the control samples and the samples prepared from PMR solutions with added styrene are not considered to be significant.

Figure 2 shows the retention of interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) for the PMR 15E composites after exposure in air at 316° C (600° F). It can be

Figure 1. - Weight loss of PMR 15E/HTS graphite fiber composites exposed in air at 316° C (600° F).

Figure 2. - Interlaminar shear strength of PMR 15E/HTS graphite fiber composites exposed and tested in air at 316° C (600° F).

Figure 3. - Flexural strength of PMR 15E/HTS graphite fiber composites exposed and tested in air at 316° C (600° F).

Figure 4. - Flexural modulus of elasticity of PMR 15E/HTS graphite fiber composites exposed and tested in air at 316° C (600° F).

Figure 5. - Weight loss of PMR 15M/HTS graphite fiber composites exposed in air at 316° C (600° F).

seen in the figure that the data for the samples prepared from prepreg containing styrene follow the same general trend as the data for the control samples. The same comment also applies to the retention of flexural strength and modulus for the PMR 15E composites (see Figs. 3 and 4).

The weight loss behavior of PMR 15M composites exposed in air at 316° C (600° F) is shown in Figure 5. The figure shows that the control samples experienced a greater weight loss than the PMR 15M/styrene samples. High temperature oxidative weight loss measurements undoubtedly reflect the net result of simultaneous thermal decomposition and oxidation reactions. Thermal decomposition, of course, causes a loss in sample weight. Depending on

Figure 6. - Interlaminar shear strength of PMR 15M/HTS graphite fiber composites exposed and tested in air at 316° C (600° F).

Figure 7. - Flexural strength of PMR 15M/HTS graphite fiber composites exposed and tested in air at 316° C (600° F).

the nature of the oxidation reactions, either a weight gain or weight loss may result. If oxidation reactions which lead to the formation of relatively stable oxidation products (e.g., oxidatively crosslinked structures) predominate over oxidative degradation reactions (e.g., chain scission), a weight gain will be observed. Conversely, if oxidative degradation reactions predominate, a weight loss will be observed. The lower weight loss of the PMR 15M/styrene samples, compared to the controls, may be due to oxidative crosslinking of the complex polymer structures resulting from the addition polymerization of styrene and the PMR end-capping monomer (NE).

Figure 6 shows the retention of interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) for PMR 15M composites exposed in air at 316° C (600° F). It can be seen that the ILSS of the composites made from the prepreg containing styrene were lower than the controls throughout the exposure time. However, the difference is not considered to be significant. The important point to note is

Figure 8. - Flexural modulus of elasticity of PMR 15M/HTS graphite fiber composites exposed and tested in air at 316° C (600° F).

that the PMR 15M/styrene composites exhibited excellent retention of their ILSS during elevated temperature exposure.

The flexural strength and modulus of the PMR 15M exposed in air at 316° C (600° F) are shown in Figures 7 and 8, respectively. It can be seen in Figure 7 that the flexural strength of the PMR 15M/styrene composites was lower than that of the control samples throughout most of the exposure time. However, the flexural strength retention of the PMR 15M/styrene composites was excellent. It can be seen that the flexural modulus of the PMR 15M/styrene composites compares favorably to the flexural modulus of the controls except during the first 400 hours of exposure (Fig. 8).

In summary, from the data presented in Table IV and Figures 1 to 8 it can be seen that the properties of the PMR 15E and PMR 15M composites prepared from prepreg containing styrene compare favorably to the properties of the PMR 15E and PMR 15M control samples.

Conclusions

The results of this investigation show that the tack and drape retention characteristics of PMR 15 Polyimide prepreg can be improved by the addition of a fourth monomer, or reactive diluent, containing an olefinic double bond. Styrene was found to be the most effective of the reactive diluents studied. Graphite fiber prepreg prepared from ethanol solutions of PMR 15 containing 5 w/o of added styrene exhibited good tack and drape characteristics after four days of unprotected exposure at ambient conditions. The use of styrene did not have an adverse effect on the room temperature and 316° C (600° F) properties of composites prepared from ethanol and methanol solutions of PMR 15.

References

1. T. T. Serafini, P. Delvigs, and G. R. Lightsey: J. Appl. Polym. Sci., 1972, vol. 16, pp. 905-915.
2. T. T. Serafini, International Conference on Composite Materials, Vol. 1, E. Scala, ed., pp. 202-220, AIME, New York, 1976. Also NASA TM X-71682, 1975.
3. T. T. Serafini, R. D. Vannucci, and W. B. Alston: NASA TM X-71894, 1976.

SESSION 17: PANEL DISCUSSION
THE DESIGN/MANUFACTURING INTERFACE:
TRANSFERRING NEW TECHNOLOGY
TO THE SHOP FLOOR

CHAIRMAN:

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No notes were taken.

SESSION 18: PANEL DISCUSSION
ADVANCED COMPOSITES SERVICEABILITY

CHAIRMAN:

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No notes were taken.

SESSION 19: PANEL DISCUSSION
HYBRID FIBROUS COMPOSITE MATERIALS:
STATUS AND POTENTIAL

CHAIRMAN:

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The panel discussion started with about 30 participants and grew to about 100 during the course of the discussion.

The panel discussion centered on seeking answers to the following issues which also constitute the agenda of the panel discussion:

- Hybrid Fibrous Composite Materials - General Consensus Definition
- Why Consider (Use) Hybrid Fibrous Composite Materials
- Mr. L.N. Phillips - Summary of his experience with hybrid fibrous composite materials (slide presentation)
- Status of Hybrid Fibrous Composite Materials: Where are we?
 - Design and Analysis
 - Fabrication Procedures
 - Limitations - Potential Problems in Using Hybrids
 - Cost: Initial, Service Life, Premium
 - Design Data Base
 - Quality Assurance

BREAK

- Potential Applications
- Research, Technology and Development Needs to
 - Resolve Present and Potential Problems
 - Meet New Applications
- General Discussion
- Summary

The panel discussion which started at about 1:45 pm and ended about 5:30 pm arrived at the general consensus answers given below for the issues raised:

ISSUE: Hybrid Fibrous Composite Materials - General Consensus Definition

ANSWER: A hybrid fibrous composite material is a composite consisting of two or more fibrous materials in one common matrix or one fibrous material in two or more matrices.

COMMENT: Uniformity of dispersion of fibrous material(s) in the matrix distinguishes a hybrid material as contrasted with a hybrid structure, for example: structural parts with selective reinforcement.

ISSUE: Why consider (use) hybrid fibrous composite materials?

ANSWER: Hybrid fibrous composite materials are used because they provide a materials with which to meet diverse design requirements while gaining overall performance advantages such as cost, weight, and ease of fabrication.

COMMENT: The performance advantages are gained with the hybrid material. Additional advantages may be or can be realized using a hybrid material in a hybrid structure.

ISSUE GENERAL: STATUS OF HYBRID FIBROUS COMPOSITE MATERIALS: WHERE ARE WE?

ISSUE: Design and analysis methods for hybrid fibrous composite materials status.

ANSWER: Available linear laminate and structural analysis methods are suitable for hybrid fibrous composite materials. Micromechanics equations have been developed only for longitudinal tensile strength and longitudinal tensile fatigue.

COMMENT: Laminate analysis requires properties at the ply (lamina) level.

ISSUE: Fabrication, procedures for hybrid fibrous composite materials status.

ANSWER: Fabrication procedures for conventional (thoroughbred) composites are suitable for hybrid fibrous composite materials; it may be a matter of extent and/or degree in special applications. Exception to this is the fabrication of hybrids from two or more metal matrices.

ISSUE: Limitations in using hybrid fibrous composite materials.

ANSWER: Limitations in using hybrid fibrous composite materials are those which arise from: (1) improper wetting between two different fibers or improper bonding between two different matrices, (2) thermal mismatch between different constituents and stresses resulting therefrom, and (3) time dependent differential displacements resulting in residual displacements which grow progressively with successive loading cycles (ratcheting).

ISSUE: Cost for hybrid fibrous composite materials status.

ANSWER: Hybrid fibrous composite materials are cost effective in many applications compared to thoroughbred composites. Even in cases where the initial costs for hybrid fibrous composite materials are higher compared to thoroughbred composites, these costs are often acceptable provided that the end-use overall performance is cost effective.

ISSUE: Design data base for hybrid fibrous composite materials status.

ANSWER: For preliminary design some data is available. However, final design data need and should be generated for specific applications.

COMMENT: Panel participants felt that a fixed design data base would deprive hybrids of their major advantage - streamline hybridization for specific designs.

ISSUE: Quality assurance for hybrid fibrous composite materials status.

ANSWER: The NDE (non-destructive evaluation) methods used to assure the quality of thoroughbred composites are suitable for hybrid fibrous composite materials. However, some refinements may be required to accommodate the different attenuation characteristics associated with each constituent of the hybrid.

ISSUE: Potential applications of hybrid fibrous composite materials.

ANSWER: The use of hybrid fibrous composite materials appears to be the direction of the future because of their unique features in meeting diverse design requirements in a cost effective manner.

COMMENT: Possible applications identified included;

Concrete forms, prosthetics, bicycle frames, mountain climbing picks, racing boat hulls, oars, tennis racquets, golf clubs, bows and in general where stiffness is traded-off for: (1) impact resistance, (2) fracture control, (3) cost, or (4) for possible combinations. Another application is where cost may be traded-off for fatigue resistance (80% glass/20% graphite fiber hybrids). The panel participants foresee an increase of hybrids consisting of glass random mat with small amounts of directional high-modulus graphite fibers for automotive applications. Major considerations for these types of hybrids are: (1) keeping the cost low and (2) mass production of parts with a high degree of repeatable and reliable mechanical properties.

Still another application, though it did not specifically come up in the panel discussion, is sparsely glass fiber weaved unidirectional graphite tapes to minimize or eliminate the electrical conductivity problem of airborne graphite fibers.

ISSUE: Research, Technology and Development needs to: (1) resolve present and potential problems, and (2) to meet new applications, status.

ANSWER: Research, Technology and Development are required (but not limited) to the following: (1) constituent material compatibility, (2) thermal mis-match, (3) rapid reliable fabrication procedures, (4) quantification of unique failure modes, (5) data base for preliminary design use, (6) structural performance data of selected structural components, and (7) long term property degradation and environmental effects (earth and/or space) resulting from hybridization.

GENERAL DISCUSSION: There was no general discussion because the panel participants agreed that a large number of related questions were answered during the extensive discussion of each issue.

SUMMARY: The chairman and co-chairman summarized drafted answers to the issues. The panel participants agreed with the drafted answers and asked that they be typed in issue-answer form and distributed to the panel participants as well as be included in the conference proceedings.